

Table 2. Prevalence based on counts of insect pests and natural enemies and on damage on rice in provinces of Cambodia, 1990 wet season.

Province	Fields (no.)	Prevalence (% offields)													
		Count							Damage						
		Insect pests			Natural enemies				Hispa	Case-worm	Leaf-folder	Cut-worm	Whorl maggot	Gall midge	Stem-borer
	Green leaf-hopper	Brown plant-hopper	Rice bug	Spiders	Beetles	Micraspis	Cyrthorhinus								
<i>First observation</i>															
Banteay Meanchey	9	100.0	88.9	0.0	100.0	33.3	0.0	0.0	22.2	11.1	33.3	77.8	22.2	88.9	55.6
Battambang	10	100.0	100.0	0.0	50.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	20.0	50.0	100.0	100.0	40.0	10.0
Kandal	68	92.6	75.0	0.0	32.4	13.2	0.0	0.0	64.7	77.9	66.2	73.5	50.0	58.8	72.1
Kompong Cham	10	40.0	10.0	0.0	40.0	10.0	20.0	10.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	10.0
Kompong Chhnang	9	55.6	33.3	0.0	33.3	11.1	0.0	11.1	33.3	22.2	44.4	55.6	0.0	11.1	55.6
Kompong Speu	16	87.5	50.0	0.0	62.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	50.0	12.5	0.0	50.0	43.7	56.2	25.0
Kompong Thom	6	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	83.3	83.3	100.0	83.3	100.0	83.3
Phnom Penh	35	100.0	91.4	0.0	65.7	31.4	2.9	0.0	77.1	57.1	77.1	80.0	54.3	94.3	71.4
Prey Veng	11	90.9	90.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	27.3	9.1	27.3	9.1	0.0	90.9	72.7
Pursat	4	100.0	75.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	25.0
Svay Rieng	10	50.0	50.0	30.0	50.0	0.0	50.0	0.0	50.0	50.0	40.0	50.0	40.0	50.0	50.0
Takeo	45	91.1	77.8	0.0	42.2	22.2	0.0	0.0	68.9	66.7	62.2	44.4	40.0	66.7	51.1
<i>Second observation</i>															
Banteay Meanchey	10	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	20.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	90.0	50.0	70.0	60.0	40.0
Battambang	10	70.0	0.0	0.0	30.0	10.0	0.0	0.0	60.0	30.0	80.0	100.0	80.0	30.0	30.0
Kandal	21	61.9	4.8	0.0	42.9	66.7	0.0	33.3	47.6	61.9	38.1	66.7	47.6	47.6	76.2
Kompong Cham	5	0.0	0.0	0.0	80.0	40.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	80.0
Kompong Chhnang	1	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Kompong Speu	14	71.4	7.1	0.0	57.1	28.6	0.0	0.0	35.7	0.0	57.1	35.8	14.3	7.1	35.7
Phnom Penh	13	30.8	23.1	0.0	15.4	7.7	0.0	7.7	76.9	46.2	30.8	0.0	46.2	23.1	61.5
Prey Veng	2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Svay Rieng	6	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	83.3	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	66.7	83.3	100.0
Takeo	20	75.0	5.0	45.0	95.0	80.0	0.0	50.0	100.0	50.0	90.0	85.0	55.0	55.0	90.0

precision of the many observers working under difficult conditions. We were confident only about the accuracy of pest identification and the presence or absence of a pest in a field.

The survey results show that the insects and diseases common to other rice ecosystems are present in Cambodia where traditional varieties are widely grown and farm inputs are at a marginal

level. Pest dynamics should be monitored under the current farm situation in anticipation of increases in the area grown to modern varieties and in input use. □

Early spraying by rice farmers in Leyte, Philippines.

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We found that 88.7% of 300 farmers surveyed in Leyte applied pesticides—mostly insecticides during the 1991 wet season (WS). The majority of these farmers sprayed early, with 77% spraying within 30 d of transplanting. Of the total sprays throughout the

survey season, almost half were applied at the vegetative phase, with the largest percentage (37%) at tillering. Farmers usually sprayed two-three times, although some sprayed up to seven times (Fig. 1).

The target pests of these early sprays were mostly leaf-feeders, which farmers perceived to be the main pest problems at tillering. The leaf-feeders that farmers cited included rice leafhoppers, cutworms, armyworms, whorl maggots, grasshoppers, and ladybird beetles. The most common insecticides used for their control were endosulfan, monocrotophos, methyl parathion, cypermethrin, and chlorpyrifos.

Studies have shown that leaf-feeding insects that damage rice plants at the early crop stages do not cause sufficient yield loss to justify spraying. This implies that most of the early sprays made by farmers are unnecessary.

Farmers sprayed early because they perceived leaf-feeding insects to cause severe yield loss. Many (86%) also believed that the chemicals they used were effective in controlling or preventing these pests. This may have accounted for the farmers' use of toxic insecticides at the early crop stages.

The majority of the farmers (81%) thought that insecticide applications

1. Frequency of sprays. Leyte, Philippines, 1991 wet season.

2. Yield and number of insecticide applications by farmers in Leyte, Philippines, 1991 wet season.

would increase rice yields. Yield data, however, did not show any positive relationship with farmers' spray applications (Fig. 2).

Clearly, farmers tend to overestimate the damage they expect from leaf-feeders. They are extremely averse to risk and respond by spraying. Our challenge is to find ways to reduce or eliminate these unnecessary early spraying for leaf-feeding insects. □

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Relative potency of three insecticides on *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* and brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*

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Insecticides are detrimental to both natural enemies and pest species. Many entomologists argue that insecticides with selective toxicity for pest species would be useful. We evaluated three insecticides commonly used in rice for relative potency on BPH and its egg predator *C. lividipennis*.

We anesthetized 1-d-old female adults of both species with CO₂ and treated them with 0.5 pl of diluted doses of chlorpyrifos and BPMC using an Arnold microapplicator. Mortality was observed 24 h later. Eight batches of 10 insects each were used for each dose. For the molting inhibitor buprofezin, last-instar nymphs in 6 batches of 10 each were used because the chemical has little effect on adults. In all cases, control insects were treated with acetone. The data were subjected to probit analysis using D. Finney's computer program.

The probit lines fit the data well in all cases except for buprofezin on *C. lividipennis* (Table 1). At the concentration of 300 ppm, only 30% mortality was observed, and the probit analysis program estimated the LC₅₀ to be >900 ppm. Regression, however, was not significant.

Probit lines for BPMC and chlorpyrifos were parallel. Data were inadequate to carry out parallel analysis for buprofezin. The estimated relative potencies for the three insecticides are given in Table 2.

Chlorpyrifos and BPMC were 2.75 and 1.25 times less toxic to *C. lividipennis* than to BPH. In the case of BPMC, the relative potency ratio was not significantly different from unity,